

About *Reduvius pallipes* Klug, 1830 (Heteroptera: Reduviidae) of Türkiye and second record from Ankara

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ABSTRACT: A species of assassin bug *Reduvius pallipes* Klug, 1830 is recorded on the territory of Ankara (Türkiye) province after 27 years for the second time.

KEYWORDS: *Reduvius pallipes*, Reduviidae, Ankara, Türkiye

The family Reduviidae belongs to the superfamily Reduvidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera). Reduviidae which is the second largest family of the Heteroptera suborder after Miridae, belongs to the Reduvidae superfamily and has 6878 species and 981 genera worldwide. This family, whose members are generally predators on small arthropods and a small portion are bloodsuckers, is known as assassin bugs. This family, which is generally distributed in the tropics and subtropics has 808 species and 145 genera in the Palearctic region (Putshkov, PV., Putshkov, VG.,1996; Henry, 2017;

Putshkov and Moulet, 2010).

In the Turkish Reduvidae fauna, approximately 66 species, 21 genera and 7 subfamilies belonging to 2 families have been recorded so far (Çerçi et al., 2024).

There is 1 species in 1 genus in the subfamily Pachynominae of the family Pachynomidae. There are 65 species and 20 genera belonging to 6 subfamilies of the family Reduviidae, these are Emesinae (5 species and 4 genera), Harpactorinae (24 species and 7 genera), Peiratinae (4 species and 2 genera), Phymatinae (1

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species and 1 genus), Reduviinae (17 species and 3 genera) and Stenopodinae (14 species and 3 genera).

Reduvius Fabricius, 1775 is a large genus of reduviid or assassin bugs and has approximately 197 species worldwide. The majority of the species are seen in arid and semiarid areas in the Afrotropical, Oriental and Palearctic regions (Weirauch et al., 2015).

The *Reduvius* genus of the Reduviinae subfamily of the Reduviidae family is represented by 8 species in Turkey, which are as follows:

Reduvius ciliatus Jakovlev, 1879; *Reduvius festae* Giglio-Tos, 1894; *Reduvius insularis* Linnavuori, 1964; *Reduvius nigrinus* Moulet, 2020; *Reduvius pallipes* Klug, 1830; *Reduvius personatus* (Linnaeus,

1758); *Reduvius tabidus* Klug, 1830; *Reduvius testaceus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1845).

Family Reduviidae Latreille, 1807

Reduvius Fabricius, 1775

Reduvius pallipes Klug, 1830 (Fig.1)

Material examined: Ankara: town center, (39°58'25" N, 32°38'22"E), 17.VIII.2024, 1 ♂, 835m, S. Kiyak leg. and det. (Figure 1) in an urban and anthropic environment. One adult specimen was found in the houses at night.

Ecological remarks: Light trap, Pistachio, Pomegranate (Önder & Adigüzel 1979; Mart & Altın, 1992; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Bolu, 2020; Fent et al., 2022)

Figure 1. Habitus of *Reduvius pallipes* Klug, 1830 a.Dorsal view b.Ventral view (Photo: S. Kiyak)

Distribution in Türkiye(Fig.2): Adana, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara Artvin, Aydın, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Edirne, Elazığ, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Konya, Kırşehir, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Siirt, Sivas, Yozgat (Hoberlandt, 1956; Mart & Altın, 1992; Önder et al.,2006; Matocq & Özgen, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2010; Dursun, Salur, 2013; Kiyak, 2016; Bolu, 2020; Fent et al., 2022, 2023; Çerçi, et al., 2022; Çerçi, Koçak, 2023; Çerçi, et al., 2024)

Reduvius pallipes was first recorded from Ankara in Haymana district in 1997 (Yıldırım et al., 2010) The finding in this study is the second record of the species from Ankara after 27 years.

Distribution in Palaearctic: Europe: Bulgaria, Crete, Greece, Italy (Sicily), Malta, Macedonia, Türkiye (European part). North Africa: Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Tunisia. Asia: Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Sinai, Syria, Türkiye (Asian part). Extralimital: Pakistan. (Aukema, 2018).

Figure 2. Distribution map of *Reduvius pallipes* Klug, 1830 in Türkiye

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